

Empowering Next-Generation AI Through Cognitive Cloud-Edge-IoT Continuum: Architecture, Management, and Challenges

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Abstract—The increasing complexity and diversity of Artificial Intelligence (AI) workloads, from generative models to real-time decision-making systems, require a transition from traditional centralized architectures to a seamless, cognitive cloud-edge-IoT continuum. This paper presents a comprehensive and unified reference architecture for AI-driven orchestration and infrastructure management across heterogeneous computing environments. We introduce novel mechanisms to optimize AI training and inference workflows across distributed edge, cloud, and high-performance computing (HPC) infrastructures, while ensuring trust, privacy, and energy efficiency. Our approach integrates virtualization, federated learning, data compression, and conditional computing techniques to support scalable, secure, and context-aware AI applications. Finally, we analyze and classify the main architectural and operational challenges involved in enabling AI-native processing across a heterogeneous computing continuum.

Index Terms—Cognitive computing continuum, cloud-edge-IoT, AI orchestration, federated learning, energy-efficient AI.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid evolution of Artificial Intelligence (AI), especially with the emergence of large language models (LLMs) and generative AI, is placing unprecedented demands on computational infrastructure. These workloads require high-performance processing, massive data throughput, and timely decision-making, often in distributed and heterogeneous environments. To meet these requirements, the computing paradigm is shifting from centralized cloud-centric models toward a *cognitive cloud-edge-IoT continuum*, where intelligence and processing capabilities are seamlessly integrated from the core cloud to edge nodes and IoT devices [1]. This transformation aims to empower AI applications with agile, on-demand, context-aware infrastructure that dynamically allocates resources, manages data flows, and orchestrates AI tasks across diverse environments. Such infrastructure optimizes latency, energy consumption, and resource utilization while upholding security, trust, and data sovereignty. Seamless integration of this continuum is essential for enabling next-generation hyper-distributed AI applications in key domains such as manufacturing, healthcare, smart cities,

and transportation. Despite its clear potential, achieving a trustworthy and interoperable cognitive continuum remains challenging [2]. Key issues include managing infrastructure heterogeneity, ensuring portability and explainability of AI workloads, supporting decentralized and federated AI paradigms, and guaranteeing compliance with openness and strategic autonomy. In addition, high-performance AI accelerators remain scarce and expensive, limiting equitable access to advanced AI capabilities. In this paper, we present a comprehensive vision and framework for developing AI-enabled management tools and architectural enablers that bridge the cloud-edge-IoT continuum. We discuss innovative mechanisms for distributed AI orchestration, energy-efficient processing, and secure, privacy-preserving AI workflows. The contributions of this paper are threefold:

- We propose a unified vision and layered reference architecture for a cognitive cloud-edge-IoT continuum that integrates cloud, edge, and IoT resources with AI capabilities, virtualization, orchestration, federated learning, and 5G/6G connectivity to support dynamic and trustworthy AI execution.
- We analyze and classify the main architectural and operational challenges involved in enabling AI-native processing across a heterogeneous computing continuum, including issues related to scalability, interoperability, energy efficiency, trust, and regulatory compliance.
- We discuss AI-enabled infrastructure management techniques and design principles, such as reinforcement learning-based scheduling, federated orchestration, and explainable AI, that support adaptive, energy-aware, and trustworthy operation across the continuum.

II. VISION OF THE COGNITIVE CLOUD-EDGE-IOT CONTINUUM AND SYSTEM-LEVEL SCOPE

The rapid growth of data-intensive and latency-sensitive AI applications has exposed the limitations of traditional cloud-centric computing models [3]. These models frequently experience bandwidth bottlenecks, higher latency, and excessive energy consumption when transferring large datasets

from edge devices to centralized data centers. To address these limitations, a paradigm shift is emerging toward a *cognitive cloud-edge-IoT continuum*, in which intelligence is dynamically distributed across all layers of the infrastructure, from high-performance cloud and High-Performance Computing (HPC) environments to edge nodes and resource-constrained IoT devices [1], [4]. The cognitive continuum envisions an integrated, collaborative computing landscape where data processing and AI model execution occur closer to data sources, ensuring timely decisions, optimized resource usage, and improved privacy. In this context, cognition refers not only to the AI capabilities embedded at various layers but also to the self-adaptive, context-aware, goal-oriented management of computing and communication resources. This continuum is designed to be *seamless*, enabling interoperable and transparent orchestration of workloads across heterogeneous environments; *trustworthy*, ensuring security, privacy, and *strategically open*, supporting data portability and minimizing vendor lock-in.

Furthermore, the cognitive continuum must accommodate emerging AI workloads with drastically different computational and data requirements [5]. For example, training LLMs requires powerful accelerators and massive datasets, typically available only in HPC or hyperscale cloud environments, while inference for edge AI or generative AI may require real-time responsiveness on device or at the network edge. Meeting these diverse requirements requires intelligent, dynamic distribution of AI tasks across the continuum. The realization of this vision requires (i) unified orchestration frameworks that support cross-layer workload distribution and resource abstraction, (ii) advanced virtualization and containerization techniques tailored for AI processes, (iii) decentralized trust and data governance mechanisms that respect privacy and ensure verifiable accountability, and (iv) interoperability standards and APIs for seamless integration across vendors, domains, and infrastructure types. Ultimately, the proposed cognitive cloud-edge-IoT continuum in this paper is envisioned as a foundational enabler for future hyper-distributed AI applications in manufacturing, mobility, smart cities, and personalized healthcare.

While individual techniques used in this work, such as federated learning, reinforcement learning-based scheduling, explainable AI, and zero-trust security, have been extensively studied in isolation, the novelty of this paper lies in their *system-level integration* within a unified cognitive cloud-edge-IoT continuum. Existing works typically address these techniques in isolated contexts (e.g., FL for model training, RL for scheduling problems, or XAI for model interpretability), without considering their coordinated operation across heterogeneous infrastructure layers and administrative domains. In contrast, this paper provides a holistic architectural perspective in which these AI techniques are orchestrated to address multiple objectives, including latency, energy efficiency, trust, privacy, and regulatory compliance. The proposed architecture explicitly models the interactions among

Fig. 1: Layers of the proposed architecture.

orchestration, learning, trust enforcement, and explainability as primary design elements rather than add-on features. This integration enables closed-loop, policy-driven decision-making across the continuum, where learning-based optimization, trust assessment, and explainability are closely integrated with infrastructure management. Therefore, this work contributes by defining an AI-native management framework that systematically integrates existing techniques into a coherent, scalable, and trustworthy continuum architecture. This system-level integration addresses a gap in the current literature, where comprehensive end-to-end designs for AI-driven cloud-edge-IoT operations remain largely unexplored. Finally, Table I compares representative related work on Cloud-Edge-IoT continuums and AI-native management.

III. ARCHITECTURAL FOUNDATIONS, ENABLERS AND WORKFLOW

To achieve the vision of a cognitive cloud-edge-IoT continuum, a robust and flexible architecture is needed. This architecture also need to abstract underlying heterogeneity, support AI-driven workload orchestration, and enable trusted collaboration across distributed computing layers.

A. Architecture

The proposed layered architecture provides abstraction, interoperability, and composability across various infrastructure and technology stacks. The proposed architecture (as shown in Fig. 1) consists of the following logical layers:

- *Device Layer*: Comprises sensors, actuators, and IoT endpoints with basic AI capabilities for on-device inference.
- *Edge Layer*: Includes edge nodes, gateways, and base stations with limited but real-time AI processing and data pre-processing functionalities.

TABLE I: Comparison of representative related work on Cloud-Edge-IoT continuums and AI-native management.

Work	Primary Focus	Edge-Cloud	HPC Included	AI Workflow Support	Federated/Decentralized AI	Energy-Aware	Trust/Compliance-Aware
Xiong et al. 2018 [6]: Edge orchestration platforms (e.g., MEC/K8s-at-edge)	Service placement & edge runtime	Yes	No	Inference-centric	Limited	Partial	Limited
Kang et al. 2017 [7]: Cloud-Edge AI serving frameworks	Low-latency inference pipelines	Yes	No	Inference	No / limited	Partial	Limited
McMahan et al. 2017 [8]: Federated learning systems for IoT/Edge	Privacy-preserving training	Yes	No	Training & aggregation	Yes (FL)	Partial	Partial
Warnat et al. 2021 [9]: Swarm/Gossip learning in dynamic networks	Fully decentralized learning	Yes	No	Training & inference	Yes (P2P)	Limited	Limited
Otto et al. 2019 [10]: Data spaces / data fabric frameworks	Interoperable data sharing & governance	Yes	Partial	Data mgmt for AI pipelines	Optional	Indirect	Strong (governance)
Hewage et al. 2025 [11]: Green AI / energy-aware scheduling works	Energy & carbon optimization	Yes	Partial	Training & inference	Optional	Strong	Limited
This paper (proposed)	AI-native cognitive continuum management	Yes	Yes	End-to-end lifecycle (train-deploy-monitor)	Yes (FL + decentralized options)	Yes (energy-aware orchestration + model efficiency)	Yes (trust-by-design + regulatory-aware policies)

- *Fog and Aggregation Layer*: Acts as a middle-tier enabling coordination, caching, and collaborative learning across clusters of edge nodes.
- *Cloud Layer*: Offers centralized compute and storage resources for large-scale AI training and model management.
- *HPC Layer*: Provides specialized, high-performance infrastructure for training foundation models and supporting high-throughput AI experiments.

Each layer provides standardized interfaces for workload placement, monitoring, and control. The architecture uses abstraction through virtualization and containerization, enabling AI workloads to be portable across heterogeneous platforms.

Orchestration across the continuum requires context awareness, intent-based deployment policies, and cognitive capabilities that adapt to system dynamics. Core components include (i) a *Multi-Domain Orchestrator (MDO)* to manage cross-layer deployment of AI pipelines, considering compute, storage, energy, and latency constraints; (ii) an *AI-Aware Scheduler* to prioritize and allocates AI tasks based on workload profiles, real-time resource metrics, and trust constraints, (iii) a *Policy Engine* to encode objectives such as energy minimization, QoS, data sovereignty, and regulatory compliance into machine-interpretable deployment policies. These orchestration components use closed-loop monitoring and feedback mechanisms, enabling the system to self-optimize according to workload demands and resource fluctuations.

B. Enablers

To enable portability and elasticity, the architecture supports lightweight virtualization using technologies such as Docker, containerd, WebAssembly (WASM), and unikernels. AI workloads can be packaged as microservices and deployed dynamically across nodes with platforms like Kubernetes, K3s for edge environments, or custom federated orchestration frameworks. Heterogeneous hardware (e.g., CPUs, GPUs, TPUs, NPU, FPGAs) is accessed through abstraction layers and device plugins, allowing AI frameworks such as TensorFlow, PyTorch, and ONNX to run efficiently with minimal code changes. Efficient execution of AI workloads in a distributed continuum requires robust data and model distribution mechanisms: (i) *Federated Learning Infrastructure* supports collaborative model training across distributed nodes without sharing raw data, ensuring privacy and reducing bandwidth usage; (ii) *Model Splitting and Parallelism* enables partitioning of AI models across multiple layers for distributed inference (e.g., split computing, pipeline parallelism); (iii) *Data Fabric and Metadata Plane* allows seamless data discovery, movement, and lifecycle management across domains, while tracking lineage and access control.

To ensure trustworthiness across the continuum, the architecture integrates mechanisms for: (i) *Zero-Trust Security*, which enforces identity verification, access control, and continuous trust assessment between all components [12]; (ii) *Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs)*, which can protect

sensitive AI operations (such as model updates and aggregation) [13] for example at the edge or fog layers; and *(iii) Explainability and Compliance Modules*, which log AI decision paths, facilitate explainable AI (XAI), and support compliance with regulatory frameworks such as GDPR, the AI Act, and eIDAS [14]. Next-generation networks play a critical role in enabling low-latency, high-throughput connectivity for AI workloads. The architecture leverages *(i) 5G/6G network slices* to isolate critical AI applications and ensure predictable QoS across verticals, *(ii) edge-native functions* deployed using service-based architectures (SBA) for efficient service composition, and *(iii) AI for network optimization*, using AI to dynamically adapt radio and transport parameters based on compute and application requirements. This architectural foundation enables the development of advanced mechanisms for workload placement, energy-aware scheduling, federated training, and trust-based data governance.

C. End-to-End Orchestration Workflow Example

To illustrate the interaction between the proposed orchestration components, we present an end-to-end workflow for deploying and operating an AI workload across the cognitive cloud-edge-IoT continuum. Consider a latency-sensitive generative AI inference service for a smart city application, where video streams are processed at the edge and model updates are periodically refined in the cloud and HPC layers. First, the application intent and operational constraints (e.g., maximum latency, energy budget, data locality, and trust level) are translated into machine-interpretable policies by the *Policy Engine*. These policies encode high-level objectives such as prioritizing edge execution for real-time inference, enforcing data sovereignty for sensitive data, and minimizing energy consumption during non-critical processing phases.

Based on these policies, the *MDO* decomposes the AI service into deployable components (such as pre-processing, inference, aggregation, and model management) and determines candidate execution domains across device, edge, cloud, and HPC layers (as shown in Fig. 3). The *MDO* coordinates with domain-specific orchestrators, such as Kubernetes at the cloud or edge, or HPC schedulers, to provision resources and establish cross-layer connectivity. The *AI-aware Scheduler* makes fine-grained placement and scheduling decisions by continuously evaluating real-time telemetry, including compute load, network latency, energy availability, and trust metrics. For example, inference tasks are placed at edge nodes near data sources, while periodic model retraining or fine-tuning is scheduled in cloud or HPC environments with available accelerators. Reinforcement learning or predictive models can dynamically adapt these decisions as system conditions change. During operation, closed-loop monitoring feeds performance, energy, and trust metrics back to the orchestration stack. If latency violations, energy constraints, or trust anomalies are detected, the AI-aware scheduler triggers corrective actions such as workload migration, model compression, or policy reconfiguration. This closed-loop

workflow enables adaptive, trustworthy, and energy-aware AI execution across the continuum, aligning architectural components with operational objectives in a practical and scalable way.

IV. AI-ENABLED INFRASTRUCTURE MANAGEMENT TECHNIQUES

To enable scalable and context-aware deployment of AI workloads across the cognitive continuum, infrastructure management must be intelligent. Traditional rule-based or static orchestration methods are inadequate for handling the dynamic nature of AI workloads, the heterogeneity of resources, and the real-time constraints of edge computing environments.

A. Key Techniques

AI techniques can improve resource allocation policies by learning from past system behavior and predicting future workload demands. Key capabilities include: *(i) context-aware scheduling*, where reinforcement learning (RL) agents dynamically adjust compute and memory allocations based on application priority, current load, and proximity to data sources; *(ii) predictive scaling*, in which time-series forecasting models anticipate workload spikes and proactively scale microservices or AI functions across the continuum; and *(iii) QoS-aware placement*, where multi-objective optimization algorithms determine the optimal placement of AI workloads by balancing latency, bandwidth, trust levels, and resource costs.

The energy footprint of AI models, especially during training, presents challenges for sustainable operation. AI-based infrastructure managers can: *(i) monitor power consumption* by using telemetry data and energy models to profile and predict power usage per workload or node; *(ii) apply green scheduling policies* by shifting non-critical training workloads to times or locations with lower energy costs or greater availability of renewable sources; and *(iii) enable dynamic voltage and frequency scaling (DVFS)*, with AI models guiding DVFS settings based on real-time performance-energy tradeoffs. In energy-constrained edge environments, approximation techniques such as early exit networks or quantization-aware inference can be activated based on resource budgets or application urgency. Centralized orchestrators face limitations in scalability, fault tolerance, and privacy enforcement. AI-driven federated orchestration frameworks provide: *(i) collaborative scheduling* through hierarchical or peer-to-peer coordination among local orchestrators at the edge and regional data centers; *(ii) swarm intelligence*, where decentralized agents use stigmergy, gossip protocols, or collective learning to allocate workloads without a global view; and *(iii) federated reinforcement learning (FRL)*, which allows nodes to learn optimal management policies while preserving local context and data privacy. These approaches enhance system resilience and reduce the

Fig. 2: An example e2e orchestration workflow for the proposed architecture.

need for raw data transmission, supporting GDPR-compliant and latency-sensitive use cases.

In distributed AI deployments, especially in multi-tenant or cross-domain scenarios, trust and security are critical factors in infrastructure decisions. AI can support (i) *trust score calculation*, based on behavior analysis, cryptographic credentials, or data/model provenance; (ii) *secure resource selection*, where AI models filter or rank nodes by trust levels, certifications, or historical reliability; and (iii) *anomaly detection*, where unsupervised models identify deviations in resource behavior that may indicate compromise or degradation. Trust-aware AI managers integrate with zero-trust architectures to continuously validate identities and enforce least-privilege execution. The complexity of AI-based infrastructure decisions increases the need for explainability and transparency, especially in regulated environments. Such techniques include: (i) *XAI for scheduling decisions*, post-hoc explanations for why a workload was placed on a particular node (such as SHAP values or counterfactual reasoning); (ii) *provenance tracking*, logging model versions, deployment triggers, and performance metrics for forensic analysis; and (iii) *policy compliance auditing*, ensuring AI-enabled decisions comply with organizational and regulatory policies through formal methods or runtime verification. By embedding intelligence in the infrastructure layer, the proposed techniques enable self-optimizing, secure, and sustainable operations across the continuum.

B. Illustrative Scenario: Energy-Aware AI Workload Migration

To qualitatively illustrate the practical operation of the proposed architecture, we consider an energy-aware AI workload migration scenario across the cloud-edge continuum as given in Fig. 3. In this scenario, a video analytics application for urban mobility monitoring performs real-time inference at edge nodes near roadside sensors, while periodic model updates are handled by cloud or HPC resources. During normal operation, edge nodes perform low-latency inference using a compressed AI model, ensuring timely decision-making and minimal data transmission. The AI-aware scheduler continuously monitors system telemetry, including inference latency, node utilization, and energy availability. At a certain point, the local energy budget of multiple edge nodes decreases due to reduced renewable energy availability or increased background load.

When this condition is detected, the policy engine evaluates predefined objectives, prioritizing energy efficiency over strict latency guarantees for non-critical inference tasks. Based on these policies, the multi-domain orchestrator initiates a controlled migration of selected AI workloads from energy-constrained edge nodes to a regional cloud or fog layer where sufficient renewable energy or lower carbon intensity is available. During migration, the orchestrator applies adaptive strategies such as batching inference requests, acti-

Fig. 3: Dynamic, policy-driven migration of AI workloads in response to edge energy constraints, enabling sustainable operation across IoT, edge, fog, and cloud layers while preserving service continuity.

vating model quantization, or temporarily relaxing accuracy constraints to reduce energy consumption. Once energy availability at the edge recovers, the AI-aware scheduler gradually redeploys latency-sensitive inference components to edge nodes, restoring the original operational configuration.

This scenario illustrates how the proposed architecture enables dynamic, policy-driven AI workload migration in response to energy constraints, while maintaining service continuity and aligning AI execution with sustainability objectives. Although no quantitative evaluation is provided, the scenario highlights the feasibility and decision logic of energy-aware orchestration across the cognitive cloud-edge-IoT continuum.

C. Rationale for AI Technique Selection

The AI techniques discussed in this paper are selected for their suitability to the dynamic, distributed, and multi-objective nature of the cognitive cloud-edge-IoT continuum. Instead of optimizing a single performance metric, infrastructure management in this context must simultaneously consider latency, energy efficiency, trust, privacy, and resource heterogeneity. *Reinforcement learning (RL)* is particularly well suited for scheduling and resource allocation because it naturally models sequential decision-making under uncertainty. Unlike static heuristics or supervised learning approaches, RL agents can continuously adapt placement and scaling policies based on real-time feedback from system telemetry, making them effective in highly dynamic

environments where workload characteristics and resource availability change over time.

Federated and decentralized learning approaches are preferred for orchestration and control-plane intelligence because they inherently support data locality and privacy preservation. Centralized learning requires global visibility and raw data aggregation, which is often infeasible or undesirable in multi-domain and regulated environments. Federated learning allows distributed entities to collaboratively learn orchestration policies while retaining local context and complying with data sovereignty constraints. *Explainable AI (XAI)* techniques are essential in infrastructure management scenarios where automated decisions impact service quality, energy consumption, and regulatory compliance. Black-box optimization alone is insufficient in these settings, as operators must understand and audit why specific scheduling or migration decisions are made. Post-hoc explanation methods and provenance tracking provide transparency and support trust, especially in safety-critical and regulated sectors. Alternative approaches, such as purely rule-based systems or centralized optimization models, offer predictability but lack scalability and adaptability in rapidly changing conditions. The selected AI techniques therefore provide a pragmatic balance among adaptability, scalability, privacy, and operational trustworthiness, aligning with the requirements of large-scale, AI-native continuum environments.

Fig. 4: Key technical and operational challenges affecting AI orchestration and sustainability across architectural layers.

V. CHALLENGES AND OPEN ISSUES

A. Design Considerations

While the proposed layered architecture defines the functional components of a cognitive cloud–edge–IoT continuum, designing a practical system also requires explicit consideration of failure modes, scalability limits, and conflicting operational objectives (as shown in Fig. 4). *Failure modes:* The distributed nature of the continuum introduces several potential failure scenarios, including partial network partitions, loss of edge nodes, stale or inconsistent telemetry, and delayed policy propagation across domains. For example, inaccurate or delayed monitoring data may cause the AI-aware scheduler to make suboptimal placement decisions, while failures in local orchestrators can temporarily disrupt coordination between layers. Mitigating such failures requires redundancy, hierarchical control, and graceful degradation strategies, which are assumed but not explicitly implemented in this work. *Scalability limits:* Although the architecture supports hierarchical and federated orchestration, scalability is limited. Centralized components, such as global policy engines or coordination services, may become bottlenecks as the number of managed nodes and AI workloads increases. Decentralized and federated approaches help address this issue but introduce additional coordination overhead and slower convergence. The trade-off between global optimality and scalable local decision-making remains an open challenge. *Conflicting objectives:* AI-native management in the continuum inherently involves competing objectives, such as minimizing latency versus reducing energy consumption, or maximizing trust assurance versus minimizing orchestration overhead. The architecture does not assume all objectives can be optimized simultaneously. Instead, it relies on policy-driven prioritization, allowing operators to dynamically shift emphasis based on application context, regulatory constraints, or operational conditions. These considerations highlight that the proposed architecture should be viewed as a structured

design framework rather than a fully optimized system. Addressing failure resilience, scalability guarantees, and multi-objective optimization in a principled manner remains important future work.

B. Critical Open Issues

This subsection consolidates the most critical open issues that emerge across all layers of the continuum as summarized in Fig. 4. *Infrastructure heterogeneity and fragmentation* remain fundamental barriers. AI workloads must operate across cloud data centers, HPC systems, edge platforms, and constrained IoT devices, each exposing different hardware accelerators, runtime environments, and orchestration tools. Despite advances in containerization and abstraction, achieving seamless portability and consistent performance across such diverse environments remains an open problem. *Scalability and portability of AI workloads* present additional challenges, especially for generative AI and large foundation models. These workloads are usually optimized for centralized, homogeneous accelerators, which makes efficient partitioning, migration, and execution across decentralized resources difficult. Lightweight execution models and hardware-agnostic deployment mechanisms are still developing.

Latency, bandwidth, and data gravity constraints fundamentally shape where AI processing can occur. Although edge execution reduces latency and data movement, it is often limited by available compute and energy. Balancing local processing with selective offloading to fog, cloud, or HPC layers requires intelligent, context-aware orchestration that remains robust under dynamic network conditions. *Trust, security, and regulatory compliance* present ongoing challenges in distributed AI workflows. Federated and collaborative learning paradigms expand the attack surface, exposing systems to model poisoning, data leakage, and provenance manipulation. Ensuring continuous trust assessment, verifiable execution, and compliance with regulations such as GDPR and the EU AI Act remains an open research and engineering challenge.

Energy efficiency and sustainability are increasingly critical across the continuum. AI training and inference are energy-intensive, while edge and IoT devices operate under strict power constraints. Coordinating energy-aware scheduling, adaptive model execution, and renewable-aware workload placement across domains requires closer integration between AI management and energy telemetry. Finally, the *lack of unified control planes and standards* limits interoperability and leads to vendor lock-in. Current orchestration frameworks are largely siloed by domain (cloud, edge, HPC), hindering end-to-end visibility and coordinated decision-making.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

This paper presented a unified architectural vision for a cognitive cloud–edge–IoT continuum designed to support next-generation AI workloads across heterogeneous

and distributed computing environments. By integrating AI-native orchestration, federated learning, energy-aware management, and trust-by-design principles, the proposed framework demonstrates how existing AI techniques can be systematically combined to enable adaptive, scalable, and trustworthy AI execution beyond traditional cloud-centric models. Beyond reiterating known challenges, this work highlights several concrete directions for advancing AI-native continuum systems. First, there is a clear need for *continuum-aware control planes* that natively integrate compute, networking, energy, and trust signals into closed-loop orchestration, moving beyond siloed cloud or edge management frameworks. Second, *policy-driven multi-objective optimization* must become a primary design principle, allowing operators to explicitly balance latency, energy efficiency, trust, and regulatory constraints instead of optimizing a single metric. Third, *lightweight and portable AI execution models*, including model partitioning and adaptive inference, are essential for enabling practical deployment across constrained edge and IoT environments. From a broader perspective, the proposed architecture serves as a reference framework for future experimental platforms, standardization efforts, and large-scale pilots in 5G/6G and cloud-edge ecosystems. Future work will focus on implementing this architecture in representative verticals, validating orchestration decisions through prototypes or simulations, and contributing to emerging standards for AI-native continuum management.

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